

THE EFFECT OF MUST SULFITATION ON THE STABILITY OF WHITE TABLE WINE

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Abstract. *The sulfur contained in sulfur dioxide forms sulfhydryl compounds and activates certain enzymes involved in yeast metabolism. In addition, sulfur dioxide suppresses oxidative enzymes and protects the must from oxidation of phenols and other substances. However, excessive amounts of this preservative in food products are undesirable from hygienic and toxicological perspectives, since they may cause unpleasant tones in the taste and aroma of beverages. In the article the influence of different sulfitation regimes stability of white dry wines was studied. According to obtained the dose of 60 mg/l is the optimum for production of quality dry wines.*

Keywords: *sulfitation, stability, dry wine, quality*

Modern trends in the development of the winemaking industry are aimed at improving the quality and stability of finished products on the global market.

As is well known, sulfur dioxide in various forms possesses antimicrobial and antioxidant activity, thereby contributing to quality improvement and extending the shelf life of finished products [5,6].

The sulfur contained in sulfur dioxide forms sulfhydryl compounds and activates certain enzymes involved in yeast metabolism. In addition, sulfur dioxide suppresses oxidative enzymes and protects the must from oxidation of phenols and other substances. Oxidative enzymes (catechol oxidase and peroxidase) oxidize polyphenols into quinones, which in turn condense and form products that negatively affect the taste and bouquet of wine. Sulfurous acid inactivates these enzymes and prevents browning of the must. However, excessive amounts of this preservative in food products are undesirable from hygienic and toxicological perspectives, since they may cause unpleasant tones in the taste and aroma of beverages [4].

Therefore, determining the optimal doses of sulfur dioxide during must sulfitation is highly relevant, as it should not negatively affect wine quality while improving the stability of finished products against various types of haze.

The main objective of the study was to investigate the influence of different must sulfitation regimes on stability against colloidal and protein haze, as well as on the physicochemical and organoleptic properties of white wine.

Research Objects and Methods

To study the influence of SO₂ dosage on the stability and organoleptic properties of white table wine, dry white Chardonnay wine materials were prepared using different sulfitation regimes:

- **Control sample** — without sulfitation
- **Scheme N1** — sulfitation at 60 mg/dm³
- **Scheme N2** — sulfitation at 120 mg/dm³

Potassium metabisulfite K₂S₂O₅, produced by the Italian company Enartis, was used for must sulfitation. It is a white crystalline powder with the smell of sulfur dioxide. Potassium metabisulfite has antioxidant properties and suppresses foreign microflora and oxidative enzymes. In acidic media, it decomposes with the release of SO₂ and dissolves easily in water, must, and wine.

When calculating the dosage of the preparation, it was taken into account that dissolution of 1 gram of potassium metabisulfite produces 0.56 g of SO₂ through dissociation.

The analyses of must and wine materials were conducted according to OIV recommendations. The resistance of wine materials and bottled wines to different types of haze was determined using standard methodologies [9]. Metal content (calcium and potassium) was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry. The turbidity of must and wine materials was determined using a turbidimeter.

Table 1. Physicochemical Characteristics of Experimental Wine Materials

Parameter	Unit	Control	N1	N2
Ethyl alcohol volume percentage	%	13.4	13.5	13.5
Mass Concentration				
Sugars	g/dm ³	2.5	2.4	2.5
Titrateable acidity	g/dm ³	7.1	6.8	6.7
Volatile acidity	g/dm ³	0.40	0.33	0.30
Tartaric acid	g/dm ³	3.22	3.06	3.04
Malic acid	g/dm ³	2.81	2.89	2.79
Lactic acid	g/dm ³	0.62	0.27	0.35
Free/Total SO ₂	mg/dm ³	5/10	8/59	8/96
Iron	mg/dm ³	0.7	0.7	0.7
pH	—	3.21	3.29	3.32
Reduced extract	g/dm ³	22.3	22.4	21.9
Phenolic compounds	mg/dm ³	182	180	179
Protein	mg/dm ³	44	44	43
Tasting score	points	7.9	8.0	7.95

The results of physicochemical analyses showed that the experimental dry white Chardonnay wine materials prepared under different sulfitation regimes were characterized by high alcohol content (13.4–13.5%). Complete fermentation of sugars was observed in all samples, with residual sugar concentrations ranging from 2.4 to 2.5 g/dm³, regardless of the technological scheme used.

Depending on the sulfitation regime, titrateable acidity varied between 6.7 and 7.1 g/dm³. The lowest value was determined in the sample prepared according to Scheme 2, where the highest dose of SO₂ (120 mg/dm³) was used. The active acidity (pH) of the Chardonnay wine materials ranged from 3.21 to 3.32.

The mass concentration of volatile acids in all experimental samples ranged from 0.30 to 0.40 g/dm³, which is acceptable for this category of wine. The lowest value was observed in the sample prepared according to Scheme 2, which is explained by the higher SO₂ dosage in the original must.

The mass concentrations of organic acids — tartaric, malic, and lactic acids — were also determined. The wine materials obtained had a high tartaric acid content (3.04–3.22 g/dm³). Malic acid concentration ranged from 2.79 to 2.89 g/dm³.

Lactic acid is a very important component in dry white wine. In the samples prepared according to Schemes 1 and 2 using potassium metabisulfite, lactic acid concentration ranged from 0.27 to 0.35 g/dm³, which was twice lower than in the control sample prepared without sulfitation.

The analysis of reduced extract, protein, and phenolic compounds showed that sulfitation regimes had only a minor influence on the production of white wine. However, during organoleptic evaluation, the wine material prepared according to Technological Scheme 1 received the highest score — 8 points. The lowest score — 7.9 points — was given to the control sample prepared without sulfitation.

Table 2. Stabilization of Experimental Wine Materials

Variant	Preparation Scheme	Bentonite + Gelatin (g/dm ³)	Turbidity Before	Turbidity After	Protein Before	Protein After	Phenols Before	Phenols After

Control	Without sulfitation	0.6 + 0.005	70.3	0.93	44	32	182	164
1	Sulfitation 60 mg/dm ³	0.5 + 0.005	71.5	0.57	44	33	180	167
2	Sulfitation 120 mg/dm ³	0.5 + 0.005	78.6	1.44	43	32	179	165

The table presents the doses of fining agents and the technological treatment schemes applied to the experimental wine materials, resulting in wines stable against protein haze. Optimal doses of auxiliary substances — bentonite and gelatin — were established. The bentonite dosage varied between 0.5 and 0.6 g/dm³ depending on the technological scheme used.

The experimental samples of dry white wine materials were treated by fining, after which turbidity and the mass concentrations of proteins and phenolic substances were determined using a heat test.

The turbidity of all treated wine samples was below 2.0 NTU, indicating that the wine materials were stable against protein haze.

The results of physicochemical analyses showed that after technological treatment, the content of phenolic compounds decreased by 13–18 mg/dm³, while protein content decreased by 11 mg/dm³, making it possible to stabilize the wines against protein and colloidal haze.

The final mass concentration of proteins ranged from 32 to 34 mg/dm³, while phenolic substances ranged from 164 to 167 mg/dm³.

Conclusion

Based on the study of the influence of different sulfur dioxide doses applied under various must sulfitation regimes during the production of wine materials, it can be concluded that:

- The most harmonious and varietally typical Chardonnay wine materials were produced when the must was sulfited with sulfur dioxide at a dose of 60 mg/dm³.
- Chardonnay dry white wine materials obtained through technological processing were stable against protein haze at a turbidity level of NTU 2.

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